

INCLUSIVE TEACHING METHOD FOR PERSONS WITH ATTENTION DEFICIT HYPERACTIVE DISORDER IN A REGULAR SCHOOL SYSTEM

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Abstract

Education is an important contributor to the development of children, including those with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). However, children with ADHD are mostly segregated in regular classrooms because of their characteristic traits. Therefore, the need to address the issues surrounding the education of persons living with ADHD in a regular school system cannot be overemphasised. This paper examines the significance of teaching persons living with ADHD in an inclusive classroom. It focused on the need for inclusive teaching of persons living with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). The paper explored the nature of inclusive teaching and what creating an inclusive teaching environment entails. It also explained the benefits of inclusive teaching to children with ADHD, the challenges to effective teaching of children with ADHD in an inclusive setting and what teachers should do when they encounter persons with special needs in regular classroom settings. The paper proffered recommendations that will lead to the successful implementation of an inclusive teaching method in Nigeria.

Keywords: Inclusive teaching; Attention Deficit Hyperactive Disorder; ADHD; Regular Classroom

Introduction

The concept of equal educational opportunities for all Nigerian citizens as enshrined in educational policy resulted to the importance of inclusive teaching methods for persons with special needs (National Policy on Education, 2013). Thus, establishing special needs education schools and mainstreaming or integrating persons living with special needs is no longer encouraged, as it promotes the feeling of segregation and lack of productivity. The current trend in education both internationally and locally is toward inclusive teaching as it yields better academic performance in school pupils and students.

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a neuro-developmental disorder characterised by inattention, restlessness, short attention span, impulsiveness, frustration, intolerance, distraction and hyperactive behaviours which occur in more than one setting with an increased prevalence (Biedeman & Faraone, 2005). The above-mentioned disorders affect significantly child's learning and behavioural abilities during educational activities. For

learning to take place, the child should be attentive, calm, focused, responsive, committed, follow instructions and remember what was taught. Unfortunately, researchers stated that about 3% to 7% of school-aged children are affected with ADHD (Strine, Lesesne, Okoro, McGuire, Chapman, Ballus & Mokad, 2006). In addition, the researchers stated that children living with ADHD are over playful, quarrelsome, impulsive, destructive and unmanageable. They leave the classroom with or without permission, distracting both teachers and students and interfering with the learning activities in the classroom setting (Bloch & Qawasim, 2011).

Teaching is the process of transmitting knowledge, skills, ability to learners as a fulfillment of their fundamental human rights irrespective of age, sex or disability. Teaching is a very important component of education; it serves as a powerful tool for the development of an individual (Ajuwon, 2008). Inclusive teaching can be defined as the process of including traditionally excluded or marginalised groups or making the invisible visible as the most marginalised are often children with special needs, girls, children in remote areas and the very poor; these invisible groups are excluded from governmental policy and access to education (UNESCO, 1990). Inclusive teaching implies that within a regular classroom, a teacher will be challenged to teach a heterogeneous group of individuals who are non-disabled, and children with behavioural problems, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) inclusive (Ndoh, 2021). The regular classroom teacher is expected to effect learning in all these categories of children whose cognitive, affective and psychomotor abilities are not functioning within the same range or degree. The regular teacher is one who has no training in special education. Regular teachers may wonder why they should be bothered with the teaching of children with behavioural disorders (ADHD) when they can go to special schools, or when in fact there are special schools and teachers for them. Such fears may be found since by training they are not equipped in the art of teaching children with special needs (Ozaji, 2005). This entails that special educators are to ensure that these teachers work in partnership with them in the management of inclusive classroom situations. When teachers are able to understand the problems of children with ADHD, they will be able to develop positive attitudes towards them, and the children will learn like any other child in the classroom.

Creation of Conducive Environment for Inclusive Teaching

A conducive environment for inclusive teaching encourages participants to feel respected and connected to each other. The participants contribute to the formation and realization of set goals for their group. Inclusiveness replaces simple physical integration of people with integration of experiences, knowledge and perspectives. It is estimated that there will be at least 200 million people (at least 18 million people with disabilities) displaced by climate events by 2050 (Balami, 2015). According to Ajuwon (2008), the growth of human society depends almost entirely on the contribution of its members. The researcher suggested that the government should encourage inclusive education by providing favourably infrastructure learning materials and educational policies. Inclusive education provides the opportunity for persons living with disabilities to learn in a natural and stimulating setting which may also increase their acceptance and appreciation in the society. Ajuwon (2008) affirmed that this will be possible where the learning environment is stimulating and teachers are adequately trained on managing the different needs that come with such a learning environment.

To achieve an inclusive system of education, the school management is pressurised to raise standards, develop social and personal skills, broaden curricular and pay greater attention to equal educational opportunities for all the students. Fortunately for persons living with personal needs, the world is shifting towards addressing the educational plights of these individuals so as to better their lives. Consequently, the National Policy on Education in Nigeria states that special needs education should be created as a formal special educational training given to individuals with special needs (FGN, 2004).

Benefits of Inclusive Teaching to Children with ADHD

The practice of including all children, especially those living with disabilities in teaching processes is imperative for several reasons. Firstly, teaching as a vital aspect of education is crucial for human capital development, personal well-being and welfare. Inclusive teaching provides an opportunity for increased quality education for all through systematic changes in the way the learning experience is planned, implemented, and evaluated (Frakas, 2014). The environment for inclusive teaching methods has demonstrated improved quality of learning and its outcomes.

Children living with disability conditions have demonstrated significant academic improvement in mainstream schools against those in non-mainstreamed. The practice of excluding children with disabilities from educational as well as employment opportunities affect the individual as well as the economy of the society. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), low and middle-income countries that do not adequately promote the participation of individuals living with disabilities in the open labour market and educational opportunities lose between 5-7 percent of annual Gross Domestic Product. EFA (2005), however, stated that a literate society translates into increased rates of innovation, productivity, growth and progressive institutional change. Therefore, excluding some individuals mostly those with disabilities from education and occupational opportunities leads to poverty. The resulting effect is that the adults living with disabilities will be unemployed and dependent on immediate family members and government welfare.

The inclusive teaching method is instrumental in changing discriminatory attitudes to persons living with disabilities as well as providing a better quality of education to everyone. The school environment provides context for children's first relationship with the world, thus enabling the development of interactions and social relationships. Research has shown that respect and understanding develop when students of diverse backgrounds and abilities play or learn together. According to the United Nation's Sustainability Development Goal 4, quality education is to ensure inclusive and equitable education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all including persons living with disabilities. Inclusive education is the key word in this goal since it acknowledges students living with disabilities and ensures they receive qualitative education.

Lere (2009) identified some benefits of inclusive teaching. He asserted that it benefits exceptional persons who are victims of marginalization by general educational problems; prevents labels and societal stigma and lessens harassment and bullying; assisting persons living with special needs in normalizing themselves both in the school setting and in the society and ensuring that pupils and students are no longer subjected to a segregated setting, social injustices, etc.

According to Agbo, Abednego, Francis and Gonet (2017), the inclusive learning environment is characterized by:

1. recognition of different cultural dimensions;
2. multiplication of learning and communication among the children;
3. positive progression and changes;
4. encouraging open and honest interaction between teachers and learners; and
5. flexibility in the teaching process to accommodate different needs and preferences.

Challenges to Effective Teaching of Children with ADHD in an Inclusive Setting

Children with attention deficit are at risk of poor grades and constant failure. Thus, Attention Deficit Hyperactive Disorder (ADHD) is characterised with inattention. More so, it is important to note that children with ADHD are

easily influenced by factors in the classroom, indicating that these children's attention is partly determined by the learning environment. In educational systems already embedded in dilapidated structures, dearth and paucity of modern teaching and learning facilities, poorly equipped, ill-equipped, poorly motivated and unqualified teachers, the prescription of the practice of inclusive teaching is a herculean task (Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council – NERDC, 2010). The challenges for the practice of effective teaching of children with ADHD in an inclusive setting in developing systems like that of Nigeria include but are not limited to the following:

Inappropriate physical environment is a threat to effective inclusion (Ojo, Agbo & Abullahi, 2013). Among other architectural designs of school buildings are also barriers to accommodate individuals with special needs. However, in implementation, the structures in public schools are not disability friendly. Equal access entails that the physical environment should be devoid of obstacles; overcrowded classrooms would not stimulate desired learning. Improved teaching-learning environment is of paramount importance in inclusive settings. This is because the environment can have a powerful effect on learners' educational outcomes.

Another challenge to effective inclusive teaching is the broken school system and structures. If inclusive teaching is to be practicable functionally in developing education systems such as ours, the broken school system must be fixed. Inclusive practices (assessments and diagnoses of special learning needs and situations, in-class specialised provisions, physical environment assistive structures, etc) cannot be put in place in regular or even integrated school settings with dilapidated classes and environments. Neither can inclusive teaching be entrenched in schools which lack basic teaching and learning facilities and equipment, and which are manned by incompetent teachers, all of which are the hallmarks of a broken education system. In other words, for inclusive teaching to be functionally implementable in any school, basic regular educational facilities must not only be put in place, but must be adequate and functional for meeting regular teaching and learning needs.

Standard prescribed textbooks, regular teaching aids and equipment, standard furniture, standard architectural prescribed classes, restructured out-spaces and environments, etc are expected to be available for all learners. Inclusive teaching requires that in addition to standard prescribed equipment for regular learning, specialised ones such as customised books and equipment for special learners, developmental and learning need assessment tests, assistive devices for learners with disabilities, etc are equally provided in the same school environment.

What Teachers should do

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is included in learning disabilities. Lerner (1993, p. 523) suggests the following as useful in assisting the teaching of children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder to function in the classroom.

- 1. Classroom placement:** Children (learners) should have their seating arrangement in an area with minimal extraneous distractions and where it can be readily ascertained whether the child is attending. This may be at the front of the room, but should be away from doors and windows.
- 2. Engage in flexible activities that accommodate movement:** Teachers should modify classroom routines to accommodate learners to move around in the classroom periodically. For instance, learners can pass paper or books around in the classroom. This type of activity breaks up the learning period and enables children to pay attention.

3. **Provide improved structure and routine:** The teacher should establish the same routine daily. On days when something unusual will occur, prepare the children by explaining what event will happen and when it will occur.
4. **Provide the learners with a daily assignment notebook:** This will enable the learner to be time-conscious and know what to do as well as when to do it. The teacher should encourage the child to make corrections to the assignments daily.
5. **Ensure the learners have focused their attention before teaching:** The teacher uses attention signals such as hand-sign, light touch or eye contact to check the level of learners' attention. Gaining the learners' attention before speaking is necessary.
6. **Ensure that parents set appropriate study space at home:** Teachers should teach parents how to establish routine studying timetables at home. Teachers should encourage parents to check if their wards completed their homework, as well as check the organization of learners school bag.
7. **Continuously use learning aids:** Learners living with ADHD enjoy studying with learning aids such as computers, calculators, tape recorders and maintain interest.
8. **Discover the learners' areas of strength and encourage their interest:** Studies have shown that children have the strength or special interest in some areas. The teacher should discover such areas and fasten its growth.
9. **Provide praise and rewards to successes:** Teachers should acknowledge good and improved behaviour. The learners should be aware of their progression through praises and rewards.
10. **Ensure feedback to classwork as soon as possible:** Learners should be allowed to know the progress they are making and have the privilege to make corrections as learning progresses. They should be allowed to discover their mistakes by themselves.

Recommendations

To improve inclusive education of children living with ADHD, the following issues should be considered:

1. There should be reorientation for regular educators in the areas of training, resources and flexibility in teaching children living with different needs and learning styles.
2. Adequate and sustainable financial support should be given to schools to support the activities and services involved in inclusive education.
3. Parents should be empowered for advocacy and assertion of child's right to education in inclusive settings.
4. There should be collective action at all levels of government and multidisciplinary sectors in generating sustainable inclusive education. This implies that the entire community should work together and participate in the design, delivery, and monitoring of education, thereby reframing inclusive education as a shared responsibility.

5. The government should remove barriers to policies that support an inclusive system of education by implementing antidiscrimination legislation, legal inclusion mandates, and policies to remove barriers in all spheres.
6. Resources should be utilised to ensure the inclusiveness and participation of persons with disabilities and those with special needs.
7. Public policy that purports to facilitate participation of disadvantaged groups, including women/girls should be encouraged in terms of the right to expression and collective bargaining.
8. Poor countries should be supported and coordinated by the rich ones at the international level in order to achieve education for sustainable development.

Conclusion

To have an inclusive environment for all, the government and other individuals should therefore collectively participate in creating a conducive full inclusive environment for all children. This will be achieved by providing funds, devices and aids, accessible environment and structures, quality personnel and techniques, firm policy making and implementation, flexible and structured curriculum and others for effective inclusive practices in Nigeria. Supportive services, and retraining of regular teachers is very important and the curriculum should be modified to be inclusive-oriented. The proposed special education policy on inclusion needs to be firmly implemented. Government and private sectors should pull hands together to eliminate most of the barriers for possible implementation of full inclusive environment for all in Nigeria and the world at large.

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